

Industry4Redispatch (I4RD)

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Analysis of techno-economic feasibility

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

HV	High voltage
MV	Medium voltage
DSO	Distribution system operator
TSO	Transmission system operator
NOOE	Netz Oberösterreich
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
RTU	Remote terminal unit

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1. Summary

The report summarizes the results of the technical and economic feasibility analysis of an extension to the DSO control center software to enable the provision of redispatch services for higher-level TSOs. A prototype implementation was programmed to assess the feasibility of the extension. We list some prerequisites, such as observability and forecasting, that are independent of the specific “redispatch” task but are nevertheless necessary. We describe the specific adaptations of the control center that are required to offer redispatch services.

Since many prerequisites are expected to be necessary in modern distribution grid operations, we make a clear recommendation to implement these features as soon as possible. The specific adaptations for redispatch provision are particularly costly to implement as there are no ready-made (programmed) solutions. The current high effort could be reduced through synergy effects as soon as a common solution is in use throughout Europe, for example. Furthermore, they rely on strong assumptions, such as accurate forecasts and that the linearization of the distribution grid is correct even under large load changes, both of which still need to be proven. In summary, it can be said that the planned approach is technically feasible.

2. Method: Prototype Implementation

Siemens has developed a prototype implementation for a sensitivity module in collaboration with Netz Oberösterreich (NOOE). In this way, we can not only better assess technical feasibility and estimate economic cost but also demonstrate it, as we will do (at the time of writing) in work package 9.

Specifically, we aim at an implementation according to the definition of Industry for Redispatch work package 5 (roughly a flow based model). In our case, sensitivities can now be calculated in the software extension (GNA - Global Network Analysis) as an add-on to the existing network control system (Siemens Spectrum Power 4). Furthermore, they can be exported to an xml format according to WP5. We use the load forecast that is in place at NOOE for day-ahead calculations.

A major challenge in this project is the calculation of the medium voltage grid, which is indispensable for an accurate congestion forecast. For NOOE, we have extended the state estimator and a power flow calculation to several selected medium voltage feeders.

In addition to the prototype implementation, we also discuss in detail all the prerequisites of the network control system that are necessary for a realization.

3. Control Center: Necessary Prerequisites

For an understanding of this report a good picture of a control center and the associated complexity is necessary. We give a summary on the core features which are relevant for redispatch.

3.1. Power System Control Center Including High Voltage State Estimator

The brain of any power grid is its control center. It is responsible for maintaining the stability and reliability of the power grid. The control center software displays real-time data on power consumption, voltage levels and system performance. It also provides tools to control power flow, such as adjusting the output of generators and switching between transmission lines.

A state estimator is the most important prerequisite for all further computations. A coherent state of the entire power system is not available by measurements alone due to imperfection, communication loss or plain errors. A state estimator determines the most likely system state based on redundant SCADA measurements in the field via least squares estimation (Wildes 1970), (Monticelli 2000). The output of a power system state estimation are voltage magnitudes and angles at all buses in the network, from which all other quantities such as current and power flows, but also bus injections can be derived. A running state estimator requires a modeling effort that cannot be

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underestimated, since a correct up to date 1:1 representation of all physical assets in the control center software is necessary.

3.2. Power Flow

A power flow calculates the system state from the bus injections. This algorithm is the workhorse for all further calculations, e.g., for the forecast for the next day. While in academia one often starts with the power flow on a blank sheet of paper, in real network operations the actual real-time system state, including topology and bus injections, is determined by the state estimator. Thus, a good interface between state estimator and power flow is necessary. The state estimator also provides the bus voltages as a starting point for iterating the power flow. In large systems, good starting values are sometimes required for convergence of a power flow.

These algorithms only sit on top of a much more complex infrastructure of a SCADA system (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) which monitors the power system. In this report, we assume that a control center software, including (high voltage) state estimator and power flow is in place.

4. Control Center: Enhancements

What we called “enhancements” are functionalities that we consider nonstandard in a distribution system, but which would be necessary for redispatch provision. These functionalities exist in some form in the current control center software portfolio, mostly targeted towards transmission system operators. These modules are also partly already used in today's distribution grid operations. However, with increasing decentralized power generation, the toolbox of the DSO needs to be extended (CEER 2015). We expect these modules to become part of distribution grid operation, regardless of the requirements for redispatch.

4.1. Load and Renewables Forecast

Forecasting is a science in itself. Load schedules are used for large consumers but also for large generation. Generation from large power plants is equally known. The impact of redispatch from industry on the distribution grid can be efficiently incorporated into a day-ahead forecast by modifying these schedules. Besides, generation from renewables is predicted from weather forecasts. A simple load forecast for small consumers uses load patterns, derived from historical data. Much more effort can be put into better predictions.

Load and generation forecasts are already in use today and are otherwise available as standard software solutions. Some engineering effort may be required for a solution that is adapted to the specifics of the region and delivers validated results. Both cost and effort could be kept relatively low with simpler solutions, but more advanced use cases, such as redispatch, are likely to require more sophisticated solutions.

4.1.1. Accuracy

A forecast has an inherent uncertainty. A partial list of factors that contribute to the uncertainty is given here.

Weather: Electricity generation from renewable sources is weather-dependent. If wind or clouds arrive earlier or later than predicted, power generation can be drastically different. Equally important, a thunderstorm with lightning strikes can cause unpredictable changes in topology.

Market: If the market changes on the power exchange, a large power producer can change its generation contrary to its schedule within its guaranteed connected load. This can lead to quite drastic changes in the distribution network.

Household loads: The electricity consumption of an individual household is stochastic. Forecasting for low and medium voltage is therefore notoriously difficult.

Both weather and market are “chaotic” systems, in the sense of Lorenz (Lorenz 1963). These systems are so sensitive to initial conditions that future paths of very similar systems lead to significantly different future behavior. Curiously, the uncertainty of a prediction in a chaotic system is one of the few things that can be specified precisely.

The prediction of household loads is based on the law of large numbers and the more households are averaged, the more accurate load forecasts become. At a more granular level, the prediction is necessarily inaccurate and skewed

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to a “mean” behavior. Additionally, there is an independence assumption at work here, which is, however, violated in the case of collective deviations from average behavior, such as in the case of holidays. (Even though e.g. holidays are included in the forecasts.)

To summarize, although forecasting is technically possible (in the sense that one can calculate a number), the day-ahead forecast comes with an uncertainty. Any method building on the forecast should be able to compensate for the uncertainties. The closer you get to real operation, the greater the accuracy.

4.2. Day Ahead Congestion Forecast (DACF)

A day-ahead congestion forecast consists of a series of power flow calculations to estimate the state of the system on the following day. For an accurate day-ahead congestion forecast, information about load, generation and topology must be gathered from a variety of sources. One is a load forecast, as described above. Planned topology changes such as line maintenance and planned switching are needed from outage management. This entire process must be automated to such an extent that a forecast for the next day can be generated without manual intervention.

While there are offline tools that specialize in time series studies, they often do not handle live data and the various input channels from the control center system well. On the other hand, while control center software usually has a study mode, it is often limited in terms of automation and flexibility required for forecasting.

A prerequisite for redispatch according to WP5 is an accurate congestion forecast. Both offline tools and control center software could be extended for the congestion forecasting process. Depending on the existing procedures and data flows, this requires a certain effort on the software side.

4.3. Medium Voltage Observability

In our discussion, we have not yet mentioned medium voltage. In all the above sections, we have had high voltage in mind, i.e., 110 kV and above. This is the voltage level that is currently represented in operation by a state estimation calculation in the control system.

Redispatch measures, if successful, will result in large and coordinated load or generation changes in localized regions. All of this is happening while medium voltage grids are already stressed by electric vehicles and generation from renewables such as wind and photovoltaics. Therefore, to avoid grid overloads, it is of utmost importance that the medium voltage grids become observable. To maintain secure grid operations, we need to assess the load changes caused by redispatch along with the system conditions created by modern grid usage.

Three things are necessary: modelling, additional remote terminal units (RTUs) and software.

All medium voltage equipment must be modeled in the control system software with correct parameters and kept up to date. Since there are many more medium-voltage installations than high-voltage installations and they also change more frequently, this is a considerable effort. Since parameters such as line impedances are currently not used for any calculation, they might not be available or accurate and there will be some effort to clean all these data.

Since most of the medium-voltage networks are currently unobservable, additional RTUs must be installed. The number of additional meters can be kept to a manageable level through strategic placement and supplemented by accurate load and generation estimates. (M. E. Baran 1996)

Finally, a medium voltage state estimation with robust algorithms tailored to the medium-voltage grid should be available in the control center software. A medium voltage state estimator must have a certain level of maturity. It must be especially robust against measurement errors and missing data. All of this is associated with considerable effort and costs. This is partly because the observability of medium voltage is “new” and partly because the medium-voltage grid is much larger than the high-voltage grid. (IEA 2023) While we consider medium-voltage observability to be necessary, it is a matter of assessing and negotiating how much of the costs should be allocated to redispatch, as medium-voltage observability will definitely become important on its own in the coming years.

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5. Control Center: Redispatch Specific Extensions

5.1. Process According to WP5 and WP3

The process according to WP5 requires that the DSO calculates sensitivities of the industry's active power injection on heavily loaded equipment in order not to overload this equipment in case of a possible redispatch call. A sensitivity answers the question: if the industrial company changes its load (or generation output) by 1 MW, how much of this 1 MW flows through different equipment (i.e., lines and such) and how much arrives at the TSO transfer point(s). Technically, this information is available from adaptations to a power flow algorithm.

Two pathways to an implementation are conceivable. The first is a modification of the legacy power flow code, the other option is to add a dedicated extension for the redispatch task. The project specific modification of the legacy code is in the best case the one with least effort, but also the most delicate. Future extensibility is limited. A dedicated extension requires larger effort in the beginning but can be set up to be more flexible and adaptable in the future. The difficulty lies therein that the extension must understand the exact same modelling as the legacy code to produce identical results. Regardless of how it will ultimately be implemented, the sensitivity calculation is in any case a (currently) non-standard solution that requires some delicate code adaptations.

The calculated sensitivities should be ideally exchanged in the form of an internationally harmonized format such as CIM or CGMES. For the implementation an individual xml format based on the ENTSO-E flow based domain documents was chosen. After the grid congestion forecast has been sent by the DSO, it is now up to the process how much further work is required of the DSO. In any case, in the long run, TSO DSO communication should be software-based. At present, it is hard to foresee how simple or complex this interface will become, which in any case must also meet high security standards.

6. Findings and Cost Estimates

The CAPEX costs of the modification of the control center software depend on many factors. One part has already been described above; this is about what is already available in the control system and what needs to be newly implemented. Distribution grids also differ considerable in their complexity and therefore also in the actual engineering time required on the part of the software vendor.

A finding of our work on the prototype was that extension of existing software, be it for sensitivity calculation or state estimation and forecasting, needs time for manual engineering. This is because in the existing system there are various edge cases which must be taken care of, e.g., specially modeled transformers. In addition, there are different data input standards in each system, which must be adapted. Due to the complexity and specialized functions of power systems and control center applications, we expect this non negligible effort to affect every extension project.

For an averagely complex distribution system in which the prerequisites are met, we can provide an estimate of prices for a complete software implementation based on the effort involved in our prototype implementation. Depending on the desired features, such as forecast, congestion calculation and interfaces, an upgrade of the DSO control center amounts to between €200k - €1m for the high-voltage level and €500k - €2m for an included medium-voltage solution. Although medium-voltage observability is a prerequisite for redispatch, the costs should not be attributed entirely to redispatch, as it is also useful on its own. The prices result from the large amount of time required to implement project-specific requirements. If several distribution systems, not only throughout Austria, are equipped with the same functionality, synergy effects are possible.

The time frame for such projects is between several months and up to more than a year, although it should be noted that network control systems are only replaced or renewed after several years and therefore longer lead times are to be expected.

From an economic perspective, it makes sense to create and commission many of the prerequisites (medium voltage observability, forecasting) needed for redispatch. A dynamic and automated grid operation is expected to be necessary in the future. Software components are orders of magnitude cheaper than the grid equipment that would otherwise have to be installed to enable capacity: Current prices for redispatch are on the order of €100m/year in

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Austria, single power transformers are on the order of a million €, and specialized software is available at similar cost. The software therefore pays for itself as soon as 1% of the redispatch costs can be avoided through optimized digital operation or the replacement of a transformer can be delayed.

The chosen approach of linearizing the distribution grid using sensitivities should be seen as a first step. AC power flows and optimal power flows with more complex approaches (e.g. successive linearization (Dommel 1968)), deliver results with even higher accuracy. Additionally, more complex designs of the coordination problem between TSOs and DSOs could be developed to further improve accuracy.

However, most of the preconditions for redispatch at DSO side are independent of the specific implementation of the redispatch coordination and must be carried out in any case. It is also expected that more coordination between TSOs and DSOs will be required in some form in the future, so this project can also be considered as a first step.

7. Summary

The technical feasibility analysis yields that the technology required for the redispatch expansions is available, at least at the high-voltage level. The interaction of the components (forecasting, grid calculation, redispatch measures) still needs to be improved. At the medium-voltage level, the technology is under development and will be available in a few years, regardless of the redispatch use case. The observability of the medium voltage is a prerequisite for (redispatch) interventions, and this prerequisite still needs to be established. A timely implementation is possible in principle, but with effort.

The authors Thomas Fabian and Sebastian Loziczky, both employed by Siemens, declare a possible conflict of interest: Siemens sells software solutions which are analyzed in this report. The authors have done their best to ensure the objectivity and accuracy of the analysis.

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